

COMPARATIVE-TYOLOGY ANALYSIS OF WORD ACCENT IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND GERMAN

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Abstract. This article is devoted to a comparative-typological analysis of word stress in English, Uzbek, and German. It reveals the similarities and differences between the stress systems of the three languages based on criteria such as acoustic correlates, placement, predictability, and functional load. The research employs comparative-typological, descriptive, and component analysis methods. The results demonstrate that, although all three languages belong to the group of dynamic stress languages, they differ considerably in stress placement and its dependence on linguistic factors. English is distinguished by a quantity-sensitive, multi-factorial stress system shaped by the mixing of historical strata, which makes prediction complex. In German, stress is primarily governed by morphological rules and is relatively highly predictable. Uzbek, by contrast, is characterized by a mobile stress system that is based on agglutinative morphology, falls on the final syllable, and regularly shifts with the addition of suffixes. The article highlights the relationship of stress to semantic, morphological, rhythmic, and historical factors in each language, and substantiates that the typological structure of a language directly influences the direction and functional load of stress. This analysis has both theoretical and practical significance for foreign language teaching methodology, translation studies, and general phonology.

Keywords: stress, prosody, comparative-typological analysis, English, German, Uzbek, quantity-sensitive stress, agglutinative morphology, phonological predictability.

**СРАВНИТЕЛЬНО-ТИПОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ УДАРЕНИЯ В
АНГЛИЙСКОМ, УЗБЕКСКОМ И НЕМЕЦКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ.**

Аннотация. Настоящая статья посвящена сравнительно-типологическому анализу словесного ударения в английском, узбекском и немецком языках. В ней раскрываются сходства и различия между системами ударения трёх языков на основе таких критериев, как акустические корреляты, место, предсказуемость и функциональная нагрузка. В исследовании использованы сравнительно-типологический, описательный и компонентный

методы анализа. Результаты показывают, что, хотя все три языка относятся к группе языков с динамическим ударением, они существенно различаются по месту ударения и его зависимости от лингвистических факторов. Английский язык отличается количественно-чувствительной, многофакторной системой ударения, сформировавшейся в результате смешения исторических пластов, что делает его предсказуемость сложной. В немецком языке ударение в основном подчиняется морфологическим правилам и относительно хорошо предсказуемо. Узбекский же язык характеризуется подвижной системой ударения, основанной на агглютинативной морфологии: ударение падает на последний слог и регулярно сдвигается по мере присоединения суффиксов. В статье освещается связь ударения с семантическими, морфологическими, ритмическими и историческими факторами в каждом языке и обосновывается, что типологическая структура языка непосредственно влияет на направленность и функциональную нагрузку ударения. Данный анализ имеет теоретическое и практическое значение для методики преподавания иностранных языков, переводоведения и общей фонологии.

Ключевые слова: ударение, просодика, сравнительно-типологический анализ, английский язык, немецкий язык, узбекский язык, количественно-чувствительное ударение, агглютинативная морфология, фонологическая предсказуемость.

Introduction.

Nowadays, in world linguistics, the issue of studying oral speech is gaining particular importance. The naturalness and effectiveness of speech communication largely depend on the correct use of prosodic means, in particular, word stress. This situation has increased the demand for a deeper understanding of stress systems in foreign languages and the identification of their differences and similarities with the Uzbek language. The study of the acoustic nature, role and functional load of word stress plays an important role in solving speech problems related to pronunciation that arise in teaching foreign languages. However, there is a lack of research work devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the stress systems of English, Uzbek and German on a comparative-typological basis.¹

The main goal of this article is to highlight the differences and similarities in the placement, prediction, and grading of word stress in English, Uzbek, and German. By analyzing these studies, foreign language teachers can develop more effective teaching methods and special exercises and recommendations that will help develop the oral skills of advanced students.

The complexity of comparing the stress systems of English, Uzbek, and German is associated with a number of factors, including the typological diversity of the languages, the interweaving of historical layers, and the differences in

¹ Abduazizov A.A. English phonetics. – Tashkent: Musiqqa, 2007. – 112 p.

morphological structures². Since these languages belong to different language families or typological groups, the acoustic correlates, place, and functional load of stress in them are fundamentally different. This requires students to understand the specific prosodic principles inherent in each language.

Although previous studies in phonology have focused mainly on studying the stress systems of English, German, or Uzbek individually, attempts to conduct a comparative typological analysis of these three languages simultaneously have been somewhat neglected. Therefore, this article highlights research aimed at filling this gap.

By filling the above-mentioned gap, it will be much easier for linguists and practicing teachers to understand the differences in stress in the pronunciation of English, Uzbek, and German, as well as the difficulties that arise as a result of these differences, and to effectively overcome them. In addition, typological comparison of the stress systems of languages also makes a worthy contribution to the development of related disciplines such as sociolinguistics, linguistic didactics, translation studies, and psycholinguistics.³

Methods and recommendations

This article analyzes the word stress systems in English, Uzbek and German using the comparative-typological method. The research draws on the scientific works of such scientists as M.A. Sokolova, A.C. Gimson, N. Chomsky, M. Halle, P. Ladefoged, P. Rouc, R. Vize, T.A. Hall, A. Abduazizov, B. Orinbayev on stress typology and phonological theory. The comparative-typological method allowed us to determine how the stress phenomenon is organized in different language systems, their universal and specific aspects.

The analysis was conducted on the basis of four main typological criteria: the acoustic correlates of stress (dynamic, quantitative, musical), the place of stress in the word and the degree of freedom (marked or free), the sensitivity of stress to syllable weight (quantity-sensitive or quantity-insensitive), and the number of stress levels and their functional load. English, Uzbek, and German were initially characterized separately according to each of these criteria, and then the commonalities and differences were summarized using comparative tables and textual analysis. The comparative-typological approach also covered the relationship of stress to semantic, morphological, rhythmic, and historical factors. It was found that stress in English is a complex system formed under the influence of multifactorial and historical layers, that in German there is a highly predictable system based on morphological rules, and that in Uzbek there is a mobile and positionally predictable system closely related to agglutinative morphology⁴. This

² Sokolova M.A., Tixonova I.S., Tixonova M.R., Freydina E.L. Theoretical phonetics of English. – Dubna: Feniks, 2010. – 192 p.

³ Jones D. An English Pronouncing Dictionary. – London: Dent, 1917. – 419 p.

⁴ Abduazizov A.A. English phonetics. – Tashkent: Musiqqa, 2007. – 125 p.

method served as the basis for creating a typological portrait of stress in different languages and formulating practical recommendations that can be used in teaching foreign languages by comparing them.

Word stress is a prosodic phenomenon characterized by a stronger, longer and louder pronunciation of one syllable in a multi-syllable word compared to the others⁵. Word stress in world languages is classified based on several criteria: acoustic correlates, the position of stress in the word, the relationship of the syllable to the stress, and the number of stress levels.

1. Classification according to acoustic correlates

Depending on which acoustic feature of the stressed syllable is the main one, languages are divided into three types:

- Dynamic (power) stress: the stressed syllable is characterized mainly by increased breath force, that is, high intensity. English, German and Uzbek are among the languages with dynamic stress. In such languages, the stressed syllable is not only louder, but also often longer. For example, in the English word 'present, the first syllable is pronounced more strongly.

- Tonic (musical) stress: the stressed syllable is characterized mainly by a change in the pitch (tone). Chinese, Thai, Vietnamese languages have such stress.

- Quantitative (length) stress: the stressed syllable is characterized by the duration of the stressed syllable. Such stress prevails in Czech and Greek.

2. Classification according to the position of the stress in the word

- Fixed (tied) stress: the stress always falls on a specific syllable of the word. For example, in French, it falls on the last syllable, in Polish on the penultimate syllable, in Czech on the first syllable. In most Turkic languages, including Uzbek, the stress falls mainly on the last syllable (however, in Uzbek, the stress also has a degree of freedom)⁶.

- Free (variable) stress: the stress can fall on different syllables of different words, and this is of phonological importance. Although English, German and Uzbek are considered free-stress languages, their degree of freedom varies. In English, the stress falls on a very wide variety of syllables for historical reasons ('family, be'come, after'noon). In German, the stress tends to fall more on the first syllable, but changes under the influence of suffixes. In Uzbek, the stress moves to the last syllable with the addition of suffixes, but in some loanwords the stress may remain on another syllable.

3. Classification according to sensitivity to syllable weight

- Quantity-sensitive stress: the location of the stress depends on the internal structure of the syllable, that is, whether the vowel is long or ends in a consonant. Heavy syllables (with a long vowel or ending in a consonant) attract stress. English

⁵ Roach P. English Phonetics and Phonology. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009. – 231 p.

⁶ Abduazizov A.A. O'zbek tili fonologiyasi va morfonologiyasi. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1992. – 136 p.

is one of such languages: in the word a'roma, the second syllable is stressed because it has a long vowel.

Quantity-insensitive stress: the stress is placed on the basis of positional rules only, regardless of the weight of the syllable. German and Uzbek languages mainly belong to this group. In German, the stress usually falls on the first syllable of the root, while in Uzbek it tends to the last syllable⁷.

4. Classification by stress levels

In polysyllabic words, stress can have several levels⁸. These levels are distinguished as follows:

- Primary (main) stress: the most strongly distinguished syllable.
- Secondary stress: a stress that is weaker than the primary, but still noticeable.
- Tertiary stress: a syllable that, mainly in American English, retains a full vowel, but does not have a tone movement.
- Weak (unstressed) syllable: a syllable in which the vowel is reduced or does not stand out at all.

In English, primary, secondary, and even tertiary stress levels are distinguished (,photo'graphic). In German, primary and secondary stress is mainly manifested in compound words ('Haus,tür). In Uzbek, primary, secondary and even tertiary stress are observed in agglutinative word forms (in our library - the primary stress is on the last syllable, weaker stresses on other syllables).

5. Classification according to functional load

- Culminative (unifying) function: stress unites the word into a whole.
- Differential (separating) function: stress serves to differentiate the meaning or grammatical form of the word. In English, 'record (noun) - re'cord (verb), in Uzbek, 'olma (fruit) - ol'ma (command verb), in German, 'umfahren (to go around) - um'fahren (to knock down) are clear examples of this function⁹.

Based on the above classification, although English, Uzbek, and German have the same dynamic stress type, they have significant differences in terms of the freedom of stress placement, sensitivity to syllable weight, and gradation. It is these differences that are the main source of stress-related difficulties in learning a foreign language.

Results

As a result of the comparative analysis in this article, the following main similarities and differences between the word stress systems of English, Uzbek and German were identified:

- All three languages are dynamic stress languages, but in English vowel quality, in Uzbek length, and in German intensity and length are equally important.

⁷ Abduazizov A.A. English phonetics. – Toshkent: Musiqqa, 2007. – 125 p.

⁸ Svetozarova N.D. Intonatsionnaya sistema russkogo yazyka. – Leningrad: Izdatelstvo LGU, 1982. – 176 p.

⁹ Wiese R. The Phonology of German. – Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1996. – 368 p.

· In terms of stress placement, all three languages are free stress languages: while in English it falls on different syllables under the influence of historical layers, in German it tends mainly to the first syllable, and in Uzbek it regularly shifts to the last syllable due to suffixes.

· English has a quantity-sensitive (heavy syllables receive stress), while German and Uzbek have a quantity-insensitive (based on positional rules) system.

· The number of stress levels varies: in English there are up to 5 levels, in German there are 2, and in Uzbek there are 4.

· Influencing factors: in English there are semantic and historical factors, in German there are morphological factors (prefixes, suffixes), and in Uzbek there is mainly a morphological factor.

· While the rhythmic factor causes the alternation of stressed/unstressed syllables in English and German, the Uzbek language is based on syllable rhythm, which limits the shift of stress.

· In all languages, stress performs a uniting (culminative) and meaning-differentiating (differential) function: in English it distinguishes grammatical classes, in German it distinguishes prefix meanings, and in Uzbek it distinguishes lexical meanings.

The above results scientifically substantiate the fact that the typological structure of languages - analytic (English), inflectional (German) and agglutinative (Uzbek) features - directly affect the direction, frequency, predictability and functional load of stress.

Discussion

The study of the stress systems of languages on a comparative-typological basis serves to provide a deeper understanding of these languages and to develop effective methods for the formation of pronunciation skills for foreign language teachers. As a result of this research, a number of differences and commonalities in the stress systems of English, Uzbek and German were highlighted. According to it, although all three languages are dynamic stress languages, the place of stress, its sensitivity to syllable weight and the factors affecting it differ significantly. In English, stress has become complicated under the influence of historical layers and has formed a quantitative-sensitive system, while in German it is a stable system based on morphological rules, and in Uzbek it is a mobile system that regularly shifts to the last syllable due to agglutinative morphology. These typological differences create certain difficulties for foreign language learners in using stress correctly.

During the study, a comparative analysis was also conducted of the different levels and functional load of stress. It was found that in English, stress serves as an important tool for differentiating grammatical classes, in German for distinguishing prefix meanings, and in Uzbek for differentiating lexical meanings. This confirms that the typological structure of languages (analytic, inflectional, agglutinative)

directly affects the functional capabilities of stress. It was also observed that, while English and German are stress-timed, Uzbek relies on syllable-timed rhythm to determine the possibilities of rhythmic shift of stress.

At the same time, there are some limitations of the study. The limited availability of sources on the historical development of stress systems for some languages and the fact that only parts of them have been preserved for certain periods may have affected the completeness of the comparative analysis to some extent. In addition, there is a need for experimental phonetic studies to fully cover stress changes in modern live speech. In the future, it is advisable to conduct broader comparative studies that also cover phrasal stress and dialectal variants, overcoming these limitations.

Conclusion

Learning a new language, especially the correct and natural formation of oral speech, and understanding the speech of speakers, poses many difficulties. In this process, the correct use of word stress is important, because it is through stress that the meanings of words are differentiated and the rhythmic basis of speech is created. To overcome this problem, a deep understanding of not only the language being studied, but also the stress system of our native language, illuminating them using the comparative-typological method, will greatly facilitate the understanding of concepts in this area. In order to fully study the rules of word stress, it is important to understand the historical development of languages - the initial state of stress and its gradual changes.

A comparative study of the stress systems of English, Uzbek, and German has shown that, although all three languages belong to the group of dynamic stress languages, they have significant differences in terms of the place of stress, sensitivity to syllable weight, and influencing factors. The quantitatively sensitive, multifactorial, and historically complex stress landscape in English, the stable system based on morphological rules in German, and the mobile final syllable stress under the influence of agglutinative morphology in Uzbek are sources of various difficulties for students. With the help of this study, these differences were highlighted and the necessary scientific basis was created for the development of recommendations aimed at eliminating them. The analysis of word stress systems in a comparative-typological and diachronic direction makes a worthy contribution not only to linguistics, but also to the development of related disciplines such as language teaching methodology, translation studies, and psycholinguistics. Therefore, it is advisable to conduct more extensive research in the future, covering phrasal stress, dialectal differences, and contemporary changes in spoken language.

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